

IMPROVING THE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE VISUAL ARTS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is discussed about expanding the possibilities of the wide use of innovative teaching methods and information and communication technologies of the teachers of visual arts in the process of teaching their specialized subjects and increasing their professional competences.*

Keywords: *visual, art, teacher, innovative, methods, professional, competence, modernization.*

The role of art in strengthening a person's world view is incomparable. It makes human life meaningful and enriches spiritually. Because art satisfies a person's need for beauty, awakens his feelings, develops his creative abilities, and leads to goodness. This creates conditions for the spiritual growth of a person, helps to solve the most complex problems in his social and personal life, and helps everyone find his place in life. For this, it is necessary to understand art, to be familiar with it.

Teachers of music and visual arts, who are representatives of this field, have a great responsibility in forming such sensitive feelings in young people. In today's rapidly developing era, in order to interest students in these subjects and develop their talent, specialists in the field are required to have a creative approach to their subjects.

It's no secret to anyone that during the time of the former Soviet Union, these subjects were treated as a secondary subject in schools, and the subject teachers explained the lesson topics equally to everyone, and as a result, talented students were relatively better, and those who mastered them poorly. Today's pedagogues put forward absolutely opposite opinions to the organization of lessons in this way.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the development of innovative teaching methods, the wide use of information and communication technologies in the educational process, and the introduction of expanding the possibilities of using educational resources.

Innovative technologies common to all of us are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and mainly interactive methods are fully used in its implementation.

Interactive methods are the so-called collective thinking, that is, the methods of pedagogical influence are a component of the educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and students.

Such a process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include the following:

to force the student not to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, to create and search;

to ensure that students are constantly interested in knowledge during the educational process;

to enhance the student's interest in knowledge independently with a creative approach to each issue;

to organize the activities of the teacher and the student in cooperation.

In order to be able to use these interactive methods in the process of teaching art classes, teachers are required to have professional competence, as well as deep knowledge and skills, as well as high skills.

A number of scientific works are devoted to the study of the problem of formation of professional competence of the future teacher. However, the interest of scientists in various aspects and aspects of this problem is not decreasing, which testifies to the special importance and relevance of the modernization and development of the continuous education system at the current stage.

In relation to pedagogical activity, the approach of separating its components as relatively independent functional types of pedagogic activity prevails. According to the point of view of V.A. Slastenin, the training of a pedagogue involves the education of the following tasks: analytical-reflexive, constructive-prognostic, organizational. The point of view taken by the author, in our opinion, largely reflects the established ideas about the structure of the teacher's activity. At the same time, researching the structure of the future specialist's professional competence means a thorough analysis of the work of the pedagogue, to determine the requirements set by the system of higher and secondary special vocational education in the conditions where the concept of continuous pedagogical education is currently being modernized and implemented.

R.H. Tugeshev stated that professional skill is competence acquired for one activity only with the help of steps taken towards the improvement of personal quality. Competence refers to the ability of a scientist to be a master of his work, not limited to his skills, but to organize work, systematically understand all problems related to his work, set tasks and find solutions to specific problems. If R.H. Tugeshev notes that the concept of competence is the same as the concept of professional skill, E.F. Zeer puts forward the opinion that professionally oriented competence and professional ability ensure a high level of professional skill. Professional competence is considered one of the four aspects of the subjective activity of a person, as E.F. Zeer pointed out, professional competence is a set of knowledge, skills and methods of professional activity related to one's profession.

V.G. Pishulin writes that professional competence, whether general or special, in many cases leads to the emergence of such qualities as memory, logical and creative thinking, reflection, agility, dexterity, perseverance, determination, orderliness and staying true to one's word, not giving in to passions, observation, curiosity, attention, seriousness and ability to deal. Like many others, we fully agree with the above points. In our opinion, it is necessary for a fine art specialist to acquire the competencies within his professional activity, i.e. he should know perfectly all the secrets of not only painting, but also of being able to convey these secrets to young students.

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